

EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS STORAGE AND INITIAL PROCESSING TECHNOLOGY IN OUR COUNTRY

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Annotation. The article analyzes the main properties of agricultural products; requirements for the quality of raw materials and methods for its assessment; scientific principles of storage (preservation) of agricultural products; modern methods, technologies for storage and processing of the main types of agricultural products, modes of technological processes, their control and regulation; changes occurring in agricultural products during their processing, storage and processing; requirements for the quality of finished products and its standardization.

Keywords: food, storage, method, technology, assortment.

Introduction.

According to the modern concept of rational nutrition, food products should not only have a high nutritional value, but also have a regulatory or therapeutic effect on the body. Therefore, in recent years, functional products have become increasingly popular. Scientific substantiation and selection of the main raw materials and functional ingredients are of paramount importance in the development of functional products, the creation of which is impossible without assessing the quality of raw materials and products of their processing.

Materials and methods.

The main raw materials for the production of flour are wheat and rye grains: about 80% of flour is produced from wheat and about 8% from rye. Grain of crops such as barley, rice, oats, buckwheat, corn, etc., can also be processed into flour, but its amount in the overall balance is insignificant [1].

Formation of grinding parties. It is carried out to maintain the stability of the technological process of grain processing for a long time and to obtain flour with desired baking properties. By mixing grains of different quality, for example, strong and weak wheat, grains with weak and strong gluten, with different vitreousness, ash content, etc., not only flour with stable properties is obtained, but also rational and efficient use of raw materials is achieved.

Results and discussion.

For the production of cereals, crops such as rice, millet and buckwheat are widely used. Since the bulk of the grain of these crops is processed into cereals, they are sometimes called cereal crops proper. In addition, cereals are produced from oats, barley, wheat, peas and corn. In some cases, they are processed into sorghum, chumiza, lentils and other crops.

The grain of cereal crops differs significantly in shape, size, structure. It is customary to consider it as consisting of two parts: the nucleus (endosperm with the embryo) and films (shells). The outer films covering the kernel are either flower (millet, rice, barley, oats), or fruit (buckwheat, wheat, corn), or seed (pea) shells.

Compound feed - is a complex homogeneous mixture of feed products and additives purified and crushed to the required size, compiled according to scientifically based recipes and providing full-fledged feeding of animals; feed is produced for almost all types of productive farm animals in loose or granular form, as well as in the form of grains, crumbs and briquettes [2].

Electronic computing technology allows you to choose the most optimal recipe option for nutritional value and optimal cost, and, on the other hand, using the specified restrictions on the optimal types of raw materials "from above" and "from below", makes it possible to more rationally use the available raw materials. Biologically active substances introduced into premixes, as well as the filler, must meet certain requirements. The main thing is to be stable with respect to

the filler and one to the other and have chemical compatibility. For example, if trace elements can react with vitamins and destroy them. Therefore, incompatible additives are usually introduced into the premix, either at the very end of the processing line, or in a protected or stabilized form.

Usually premixes are prepared at the rate of 1% addition to the feed mixture. In this case, biologically active substances are first weighed, and then one tenth of the filler. The components are thoroughly crushed and sieved, and then mixed and adjusted to the desired weight by adding filler, mixed again and only then packaged in bags.

Provided sufficient grinding of the filler and micro-additives, a stable mixture is formed only after thorough mixing. In this case, the type of mixer is not so important as the size of the particles of the filler and microingredients, etc [3].

If the screw or mixer drum rotates too fast, the particles are not distributed well, as centrifugal forces begin to act.

If a premix is prepared containing all biologically active substances, then vitamins and amino acids are first mixed with the filler, and then salts of microelements are introduced into the mixture.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the main grain components of the feed are wheat, barley, oats, rye, and triticale. The limiting factor for the widespread use of these components in the production of animal feed is the presence of fiber, beta - glucans and pentosans in them. In addition, phosphorus in vegetable feed is in the form of a complex organic compound of phytin, which is poorly absorbed by birds, which, if phosphorus supplements are deficient, leads to a violation of mineral metabolism and an improvement in the quality of the shell.

Wheat, rye, triticale have a high content of soluble non-starchy polysaccharides - viscous arabinosylans, when they enter the intestine, they give high viscosity to its contents - chyme, and have a harmful effect on the absorption and assimilation of nutrients by the body, mainly fat. It is also well known that amposaccharides of the refined group have a negative effect on digestion [4].

Conclusion.

Numerous experiments and studies have confirmed that it is possible to increase the availability of energy and other nutrients, as well as phytic phosphorus from compound feed containing components that are difficult to hydrolyze, with the help of enzyme preparations. Enzymes (enzymes) are protein substances produced by plants, animals and microorganisms that can speed up chemical reactions without being part of the final products.

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